

Evaluation of the pigments concentration in the Iris species native to Iran

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Abstract

The color and morphology flower is one impressive feature the flower industry. Accumulation of pigments in flowers is determining one of the major factors in flower color. In this experiment accumulation of pigments were evaluated in the Iris species native to Iran. The following were properties were measured, accumulation of chlorophyll a, b and all , anthocyanins, carotenoids of leaves and flowers and heritability percent. The results showed that the *Iris acutiloba* was highest concentration anthocyanins and carotenoids of pigments than the other species. Most of the heritability was observed of the b chlorophyll pigments.

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Introduction

Iris is a perennial plant of the Iridaceae family (Khalighi, 2003). Iris flower has a wide range of colors including white, yellow, orange, brown and black (Austin, 2005). Accumulation of pigments in flowers are the major factors in determining flower color (Ashtakala and Forward, 1971). Flower color is the main factor in determining the market value of ornamental plants and flowers (Ying tu and Kuang vang, 2006). Flower colors are three main classes including flavonoids, carotenoids and betalain (Scolnik and Bartley, 1995). So far, the flower has identified about 600 types of carotenoids, 7000 kinds of flavonoids and more than 500 kinds of anthocyanins (Davis, 2004).

Flower color is mainly determined by anthocyanins (Yukihisa *et al.*, 2007). The pathway leading to anthocyanidin 3-glucoside is generally conserved among higher plant species (Grotewold 2006, Tanaka and Brugliera 2006). Flavonoids consist of more than 10 classes of compounds, Anthocyanins confer orange, red, magenta, violet and blue colors (Yoshikazu, 2009). Petunia lacks brick red/orange varieties due to the lack of pelargonidin-based anthocyanins because their dihydroflavonol 4-reductases (DFRs) do not utilize dihydrokaempferol as a substrate (Forkmann and Heller 1999, Johnson *et al.* 1999).

Carotenoids are plant pigments that function as antioxidants, hormone precursors, colorants and essential components of the photosynthetic apparatus (Crispin and Barry, 2006).

The highest total flavone content of *Campanula isophylla* was reached at anthesis, after which it remained almost constant, but with some changes in the proportion of individual compounds (Justesen *et al.*, 1997).

Flower color is one of the most attractive features of ornamental plants. Flower color is changed, one of the main objectives of the Iris flower breeding. The purpose of this experiment, is investigated the

accumulation of the pigments and the heritability of the pigments in the 8 Iris species.

Material and Methods

Plant material

The 8 Iris species were collected from Zanjan province of Iran country and were planted in field of Khorramdarreh city and are accurately identified by using the resources of Flora Iranica, Tulipa and Irises of Iran and the site of international plant name. The experiment was conducted to purpose investigation of pigments concentration and their heritability percent in 8 species of Irises of 10 replications.

The following properties were measured, accumulation of chlorophyll a, b and all, anthocyanins, carotenoids, heritability percent.

Chlorophyll a, b and all and Carotenoids measurement

Chlorophyll content is obtained by rinsed in 80% acetone solution and measuring its absorbance using spectrophotometer at 645 and 663 nm (Arnon, 1949), and Carotenoids content of petals and leaf at 480 and 510 nm, estimation value were calculated according to the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Chlorophyll a mg/g} &= 12.7(A_{663}) - 2.69(A_{645}) \times V / 1000 \times 10 \\ \text{Chlorophyll b mg/g} &= 22.9(A_{645}) - 4.68(A_{663}) \times V / 1000 \times 10 \\ \text{Chlorophyll all mg/g} &= 20.2(A_{645}) - 8.02(A_{663}) \times V / 1000 \times 10 \\ \text{Carotenoids mg/g} &= 7.6(A_{480}) - 1.49(A_{510}) \times V / 1000 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

Anthocyanins measurement

Anthocyanins is extracted with acidified methanol and measuring its absorbance using spectrophotometer at 550 nm (Wagner, 1979), estimation value were calculated according to the following formula

$$A = \epsilon bc$$

Heritability percent

Heritability percent estimation value was calculated according to the following formula (Aghahi *et al.*, 2012):

$$h^2 = \frac{\sigma_g^2}{\sigma_p^2}$$

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed by the MSTAT-C software, and the comparison means was done Duncans multiple range (DMRT) test and Graphs were plotted using Excel software.

Results and discussion

Chlorophyll a, b and all analysis

Results has revealed that Irises a high color variation. Similar results were also reported by Yabochi *et al* (2006) of japanies Irises. The chlorophyll a, b and all concentration in *Iris meda 2* were lower than in other species. But the amount of chlorophyll a, b and all accumulation did not differ significantly from each other species(Fig 1). *Iris acutiloba*, *Iris meda 1* and *Iris meda 3* species were with the highest concentration of chlorophyll b in their leaves (Table 1). The chlorophyll b concentration in the leaves are suitable for the study of the plant resistance to environmental conditions (Damir *et al*, 2008). Most of the heritability was of the chlorophyll b concentration in leaves (Table 2). Which confirms the necessity and importance of chlorophyll b in photosynthesis and resistance to environmental conditions.

Table 1. Comparison of the accumulation of pigments.

Species	Chlorophyll a mg/g	Chlorophyll b mg/g
<i>I.reticulata 1</i>	23.91 ab	8.16 def
<i>I.reticulata 2</i>	28.47 a	13.36 bcd
<i>I.pseudocaucasica</i>	26.90 a	11.12 cdef
<i>I.persica</i>	27.41 a	12.46 bcde
<i>I.acutiloba</i>	26.99 a	17.38 ab
<i>I.meda 1</i>	27.95 a	17.77 ab
<i>I.meda 2</i>	18.09 b	7.04 ef
<i>I.meda 3</i>	25.66 ab	21.16 a

Means followed by similar letters in each column are not significantly at 1% level by using Duncan multiple range test

Table 2. Heritability percent of traits.

trait	Heritability %
Chlorophyll a	55.44
Chlorophyll b	90.06
Chlorophyll all	76.54
Anthocyanin	50.79
Cartenids of leaves	52.95
Cartenids of flowers	61.04

Fig. 1. accumulation chlorophyll all and carotenoids at leaves of Iris species.

Anthocyanin analysis

Iris acutiloba and *Iris reticulata 2* was not significant difference together in the rate of accumulation of anthocyanins in the petals, but compared to other species had the highest rate of accumulation of anthocyanins (Fig 2).Anthocyanins are common floral pigments that give rise to blue, purple and red colors and flavnoid biosynthetic pathway responsible for anthocyanin pigmentation is highly conserved (Winkel-shirley, 2002). Anthocyanin structure, type and concentration, co- existing compounds (co-pigments), metal ion type and concentration, PH of vacuoles anthocyanin localization and shape of surface cells all contribute to final flower colour (Yoshida *et al*, 2009).

Fig. 2. accumulation anthocyanin of Iris species of flowers.

Cartenoids analysis

The highest cartenoids concentration was observed in *Iris meda* 1 and *Iris pseudocaucasica* leaves (Fig 1). But the highest cartenoids concentration was observed in *Iris acutiloba* flowers (Fig 3). The accumulation of cartenoids in leaves was negatively correlated with the accumulation of cartenoids in flower.

Fig. 3. accumulation cartenoids of Iris species petals.

Conclusion

Then the study eight Iris species, that found the *Iris acutiloba* was highest accumulation of anthocyanin and cartenoids in petals to other species. So can of *Iris acutiloba* the breeding work used of the change the Iris color flowers.

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